

Case Report

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Ultrasound evidence of a funicular cord hydrocele in a six-week infant

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Abstract

Scrotal hydrocele is, in infants and children, a frequent benign condition. Decidedly rarer are the forms of hydrocele where there is not residual communication with tunica vaginalis. A 6-week-old infant presented with painless acute onset of inguinal swelling covered by erythematous skin. The scrotal ultrasound showed a 26x21x10 mm lobulated-saccate fluid collection in the context of the right spermatic funiculus, communicating with peritoneal cavity, compatible with cord hydrocele in its funicular variant. Hydrocele of the spermatic cord results from failure to close the vaginal process. Objective examination and ultrasonography can provide differential diagnosis from other conditions that can cause inguinal-scrotal swelling such as inguinal hernia, varicocele, testicular torsion, epididymis cyst, and spermatocele. Treatment options range from conservative measures to surgery, mostly depending on clinical evolution and subtypes.

Keywords: Ultrasound; Funicular hydrocele; Spermatic cord; Infants.

Introduction

Hydrocele is an abnormal collection of serous fluid within the tunica vaginalis. It is a benign and relatively common condition, especially in children and adult men after age 40. Hydrocele can be congenital or acquired (secondary to trauma, infection, surgery, or testicular disease) [1]. In the newborn/ infant's era, hydrocele is almost always congenital and related to a failure to reabsorb or incomplete closure of the peritoneal-vaginal duct. During fetal development, testes in male infants descend from the abdominal cavity into the scrotum. This descent is accompanied by the formation of a peritoneal extension known as the processus vaginalis, which allows the abdominal lining to protrude into the scrotal sac. Under normal circumstances, the processus vaginalis undergoes obliteration before birth. A hydrocele arises when the processus vaginalis fails to close completely or when residual peritoneal fluid remains surrounding the testis at the time of delivery [2-4].

Hydroceles can be classified into three main types (Figure 1).

Communicating hydrocele: This type results from persistence of a patent processus vaginalis, allowing free movement of fluid between the abdominal cavity and the tunica vaginalis. It is more commonly observed in premature infants. The volume of the hydrocele may vary depending on intra-abdominal pressure-enlarging during straining or crying and diminishing at rest or during sleep. In cases where the patent processus is sufficiently wide, abdominal viscera, such as intestinal loops, may herniate into the scrotum, constituting an inguinal hernia.

Non-communicating hydrocele: This form arises when the connection between the peritoneal cavity and the scrotum has been completely obliterated. In such cases, peri-testicular fluid becomes trapped without any ongoing exchange with the abdominal cavity. These hydroceles are typically benign and self-limiting, with spontaneous resolution over time. A specific

Figure 1: The diagrams illustrate the range of anomalies resulting from incomplete closure of the processus vaginalis. **(a)** Normal anatomy: Tunica vaginalis is normally developed, the funicular portion of the processus vaginalis is completely obliterated, no fluid come from peritoneal cavity. **(b)** Scrotal communicating hydrocele: The processus vaginalis remains fully patent, creating a continuous communication between the peritoneal cavity, superiorly, and the tunica vaginalis, inferiorly, allowing the fluid to accumulate in the scrotum. **(c)** Scrotal non-communicating hydrocele: the connection between the peritoneal cavity and the scrotum has been completely obliterated. The fluid accumulates only in the scrotum. **(d)** Encysted hydrocele of spermatic cord: The funicular process is completely isolated, with no communication to either the peritoneal cavity or the tunica vaginalis, resulting in a localized fluid-filled cyst along the spermatic cord. **(e)** Funicular hydrocele of spermatic cord: The funicular process is open and communicates with the peritoneal cavity, but there is no connection with the tunica vaginalis. Fluid is confined to the funicular tract.

variant, known as a reactive hydrocele, may occur during childhood as a response to inflammation of the scrotum, often secondary to trauma or infection.

- **Spermatic cord hydrocele (hydrocele of the cord):** Less frequent than scrotal hydroceles, this type involves fluid accumulation along the spermatic cord, which comprises the vas deferens and associated vessels. Two subtypes are recognized:

- **Encysted cord hydrocele:** Here, fluid collects within the spermatic cord without any communication with the peritoneal cavity or the tunica vaginalis. The trapped fluid remains localized and is typically reabsorbed spontaneously, often within the first year of life.

- **Funicular cord hydrocele:** In this case, the proximal portion of the processus vaginalis remains patent, maintaining a potential connection between the peritoneal cavity and the spermatic cord, but not with the tunica vaginalis. As with communicating hydroceles, the size may fluctuate with changes in intra-abdominal pressure. This subtype is less likely to resolve spontaneously and often requires surgical correction.

We report the sonographic features of a funicular hydrocele in a 6-week newborn, with a brief literature review.

Case presentation

A 6-week-old infant presented with his parents at Radiology Department of San Felice a Canello Hospital following acute onset of inguinal swelling covered by erythematous skin. His parents denied vomiting or constipation. Birth history was unremarkable, and were not significant medical, surgical, or familial history. On physical examination, the abdomen was soft, non-tender, non-distended, and bowel sounds were active and normal. Both testes were normally descended and non-tender on palpation. A soft mass was palpable in the right inguinal canal. Therefore, a scrotal ultrasonography was performed. In the context of the right spermatic funiculus, there was evidence

of an anechoic, avascular, lobulated-saccate fluid collection of about 26x21x10 mm that departed from the peritoneum to the inguinal region, with no internal solid elements. Concomitant small multiple lymph nodes of reactive appeared in bilateral inguinal region. The findings were compatible with funicular hydrocele of the spermatic cord (Figure 2).

Discussion

While scrotal hydrocele is a common condition in neonates and children, spermatic cord hydrocele is a rare anomaly. We reported a case of a spermatic cord hydrocele in its funicular variant in a 6-week baby, presenting with painless inguinal swelling, erythema, diagnosed with ultrasound. Active surveillance was the first choice. Few other cases of cord hydrocele have been described in the literature, mainly represented

Figure 2: Longitudinal grayscale ultrasound of the right inguinal region demonstrates an anechoic, avascular fluid collection with no internal solid elements.

Table 1: Relevant literature on spermatic cord hydrocele.

Author, year	Study type	n. cases	Age	Variant	Imaging	Treatment
Singh, 2010 [5]	Case report	1	3 years	encysted	Rx US	surgery
Chang, 2010 [6]	Retrospective monocentric	20	1-54 months	5 encysted 7 funiculars 8 mixed	US	surgery
Rathaus, 2021 [7]	Retrospective monocentric	27	6 months-13 years	24/27 encysted 3/27 funicular	US	23 surgeries 3 US FUP 1 lost at FUP
Sugianto, 2021 [8]	Case report	1	3 years	encysted	US	surgery
Chairul, 2023 [9]	Case report	1	2 years	encysted	US	surgery
Adhikari, 2024 [10]	Case series	5	9 months-12 years	encysted	US	surgery

FUP: Follow-Up; US: Ultrasonography.

by the encysted variant (Table 1), although its benign clinical course could make its incidence underreported.

US was performed in all cases, showing its prominent role in differential diagnosis [7]. US differential diagnosis between a funicular hydrocele and an indirect inguinal hernia may be difficult and sometimes impossible. Two US findings are, however, characteristic: the presence of a loculated fluid collection and of a closed internal ring. US examination also excludes the possibility of a loculated hydrocele secondary to fibrous adhesions, an abscess, or a Para epididymal cyst.

Symptoms of funicular and encysted cord hydrocele can be similar but may differ, since one may vary in size, while the other may not, respectively. On examination, the patient's abdomen is generally soft, nontender, and nondistended, with normal active bowel sounds [5]. Management of hydroceles varies based on the specific type. Communicating scrotal hydroceles are managed similarly to inguinal hernias, following standard surgical principles. Surgical intervention is generally indicated for non-communicating hydroceles that persist beyond 12 to 18 months or demonstrate progressive enlargement. Encysted cord hydroceles, which typically resolve spontaneously by the age of one, can be managed conservatively. In the case of funicular hydroceles, active surveillance can be the first choice, but more often elective surgical excision or herniotomy is recommended to reduce the risk of future development of an acquired indirect inguinal hernia. It has been reported 16.1% of moderate or severe hydrocele surgery complications within 90 days after surgery [11]. Although less commonly performed, laparoscopic repair has been reported. In the series, described by Chang et al. [6], consisting of 20 consecutive male infants or boys, ranging in age from 38 days to 54 months, surgery for 16 irreducible cord hydroceles was done via the open approach, whereas the remaining 4 were reducible and laparoscopy was performed.

Conclusion

Reported here is a case of a rare funicular cord hydrocele in a 6-week infant, diagnosed with ultrasound. Existing literature showed that hydrocele of the spermatic cord is mainly congenital, with typical presentation in infancy or early life. Studies include case reports, case series, or retrospective cohorts, with insights into ultrasound diagnosis, classification and management. Ultrasonographic examination plays a major role in differential diagnosis and their continuation.

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